

Code-Switching in English as a Second Language: Uncovering the Benefits and Setbacks

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Abstract. Language learning has been figuratively described as crossing the bridge from the known (L1: first language) to the unknown (L2: second language). However, a thin line exists between a learner's first and second language. Along with that are several converging and clashing studies regarding whether using L1 obstructs the learning of L2. Through a qualitative phenomenological study, the researcher unfurled the experiences, coping mechanisms, and insights about code-switching from the English teachers' standpoint. The study participants were ten (10) secondary English teachers currently teaching in a secondary school belonging to cluster 14 under Buhangin District. Extracted narratives from the interview revealed teachers' experiences with code-switching: the repetitive, affective function impedes the students' learning of L2 and causes a decline in students' language proficiency and confidence. Meanwhile, the coping mechanisms were effective communication, encouraging the utilization of L2, and minimizing code-switching. The insights were code-switching as an emerging language pedagogy and applying the right function of the said sociolinguistic phenomena. The study's findings would benefit the learners, as they would realize the positive and negative effects of code-switching. They may also discover how code-switching may support or hinder their language learning. Most importantly, the findings would raise awareness among the learners about how code-switching should be utilized to assist them in their language learning journey.

KEY WORDS

1. code-switching 2. first language 3. second language 4. language proficiency

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1. Introduction

The choice of language used in the teaching and learning process is of utmost importance for supporting learners' knowledge acquisition, comprehension, skill development, and ability to communicate acquired knowledge in assignments and exams effectively. Learners not skilled in the language of instruction may experience difficulties in their educational growth.

When teachers and students are both fluent in the language of instruction, the quality and relevance of instruction significantly improve. In these situations, teachers are better able to give detailed explanations and encourage in-depth discussions while students actively participate in group knowledge development through engaging classroom interactions. Code-switching,

the practice of alternating between two or more languages, has long been a subject of discussion and debate in the realm of English as a Second Language (ESL) instruction. This language phenomenon can be a two-edged sword, providing several benefits as well as serious drawbacks. The repercussions of code-switching as a teaching approach must be carefully considered by educators in EFL classrooms since the main objective is to enhance English language acquisition. Code-switching has proven a successful teaching and learning strategy, especially in institutions that use a second language as the primary instruction medium. This strategy is beneficial when students have trouble communicating through the only medium of instruction (Ogechi, 2019). In the global scene, the utilization of the student's native language or first language (L1) and the target language is often regarded as complementary, with its appropriateness contingent upon the specific characteristics and stages of the language learning process. As a result, the *Asian Journal of Education and Social Studies* (2023) noticed that instructors occasionally use students' L1 in EFL classrooms for task explanations, task organization, and behavior management. They do so because they believe that doing so helps the students better achieve the language-related learning objectives of the lesson's primary focus. In the case of Fareed et al. (2018), some instructors have suggested that code-switching helps pupils, particularly those with poor self-esteem who are experiencing anxiety, nervousness, fear, and reluctance. Several converging studies have emerged as to how teachers should perceive code-switching and how would it affect the language learning of students. Meanwhile, in the Philippines, an examination of the functions of code-switching in English language classes indicates that code-switching does not inherently signify a lack of competence in English. Instead, it is employed with a specific purpose and can even serve as a valuable resource in the teaching and learning of English in the Philippines (Macaro, 2019). However, while code-switching has specific benefits for improving communication in multicultural and multilingual classrooms, providing a pleasant learning environment, and promoting comprehension, it also has some drawbacks. When compared to classes where English is used consistently throughout teaching, excessive code-switching in the classroom can prevent students from using the English language to its fullest potential. Excessive code-switching may cause pupils to rely more heavily on their native tongue than on English, which could hinder their language ability and development. It is in line with the idea of Yaakub et al. (2018) that code-switching is perceived to have disadvantages, including a potential overreliance on students' first language (L1) and the idea that it may deprive students of beneficial opportunities to practice the target language. In educational settings, where the aim is to strike a compromise between linguistic clarity and the development of language fluency in the target language, these difficulties highlight the significance of utilizing code-switching sparingly. The dynamics of code-switching in educational settings are complex, exhibiting both advantages and disadvantages. However, there is a notable research gap in the Philippines. That is the limited exploration of the specific benefits and setbacks of code-switching in English language instruction from the teachers' perspective. In the local scene, a qualitative study at the University of the Immaculate Conception in Davao City delved into the viewpoints and motives behind students' use of code-switching in the classroom. The research, which involved in-depth interviews and focus group discussions with second-year college students, revealed that students often resorted to code-switching as a cognitive strategy to bridge gaps in understanding and clarify ideas. The study highlighted that language anxiety and reliance on their first language were

primary motives for students to code-switch, suggesting a need for educators to foster an environment that encourages consistent use of the target language while reducing reliance on L1 (Corpuz et al., 2018). Hence, the limited examination of the unique advantages and drawbacks of code-switching in English language instruction from the perspective of instructors is a significant research gap in the Philippines. While code-switching's effects on students are frequently discussed in the literature, little is known about how teachers view and use this pedagogical tool. It may be possible to shed light on the effectiveness of code-switching as a teaching strategy and contribute to developing more specialized language teaching methods by understanding teacher viewpoints on the benefits and drawbacks of the practice in the Philippine educational system. Examining this unexplored aspect would assist in informing instructional techniques that are more in line with the demands of both teachers and students in the Philippines and offer insightful information on the difficulties of code-switching in EFL classrooms. This researcher desires to illuminate the perceived experiences and coping mechanisms of code-switching from the English teachers' perspective. The researcher also hopes that this study benefited the identified sectors of the academe. This includes the educational leaders, school heads, teachers, other stakeholders, and future researchers. Educational leaders would benefit from the findings of this study as it can offer them a substantial contribution towards providing scaffolding in the field of language learning. Moreover, the findings of this study might help the school heads or principals to be aware and informed of the study's topic and it could serve as their guidance in providing ample assistance and help to teachers. It may also enlighten the teachers on what and how to assist students to yield better results in terms of their language learning. The various internal and external stakeholders may also provide

better support and assistance to enhance and achieve academic goals in the field of language learning. Finally, this would be helpful for future researchers as an additional contribution to their references for future research in the field of language learning, specifically about code-switching, offering them a substantial contribution to their academic arsenal.

1.1. Purpose of the Study—This study's purpose was to investigate teachers' experiences and coping mechanisms regarding the use of code-switching in English as a Second Language (ESL) classrooms. By thoroughly investigating the perspectives and behaviors of the English teachers from Teofilo V. Fernandez National High School in Buhangin District, the study intends to investigate the advantages and disadvantages of code-switching as viewed by teachers. This study aims to understand how educators in EFL environments see the importance of code-switching in aiding language education and classroom management by concentrating entirely on the teacher's point of view. The research's findings are intended to provide important knowledge to pedagogical practices and recommendations for teachers, ultimately boosting their ability to use code-switching as a teaching tool in EFL classes effectively. The data collection was focused on the experiences and coping mechanisms regarding code-switching through the lens of the teachers. The findings of this phenomenological study contribute to a deeper understanding of the authentic experiences of the teachers about the use of code-switching. The insights gained from this research can potentially inform educational leadership practices, professional development initiatives, and policies aimed at improving teachers' strategies in teaching English.

1.2. Research Questions—The purpose of this study was to investigate secondary school teachers' experiences in ESL classrooms with a particular emphasis on the phenomena of code-switching. The following primary questions

were the focus of the research:

- (1) What are the lived experiences of teachers who employ code-switching in their English as a Second Language (ESL) classroom?
- (2) What does secondary English employ the coping mechanisms teachers for code-switching in their English as a Second Language (ESL) classroom?
- (3) What are the language learning insights formulated from the findings of the study?

For a more comprehensive understanding, the following terms were described operationally. Code-switching refers to the practice of switching back and forth between two languages or between two dialects or registers of the same language at one time. Code-switching occurs far more often in conversation than in writing (Nordquist, 2019). First language (L1). The language that someone learns to speak first (Ene, 2020). Second language (L2). This refers to any language that a person uses other than a first or native language (Nordquist, 2020).

1.3. Review of Significant Literature—

1.3.1. Teachers' Experiences in Employing Code-Switching—English, as a global lingua franca, is integral to communication in multilingual settings, particularly in education. Teachers in ESL environments often focus on developing learners' speaking skills, frequently using code-switching—the practice of alternating between two or more languages. Code-switching aids in clarifying meaning, expressing identity, and managing classroom dynamics, as noted by García and Wei (2018). Research by Sayer and Ban (2020) suggests that code-switching can be a valuable pedagogical tool, facilitating comprehension by allowing learners to use their first language (L1) to support second language (L2) learning. However, excessive reliance on L1 can hinder L2 proficiency, as pointed out by Turnbull and Dailey-O'Cain (2020), who advocate for a balanced approach.

In the social context of classrooms, code-switching builds inclusivity and community among learners from diverse linguistic backgrounds (García and Li Wei, 2020). Yet, some

educators, like McKay and Wong (2019), view it as a deviation from standard language norms. Despite this, Creese and Blackledge (2018) argue for translanguaging, which encourages fluid use of learners' linguistic repertoires. Sert (2005, as cited in Istifci 2019) and Mattson and Burenhult (1999, as cited in Shafi Kazmi and Asif 2019) identify code-switching's functions in topic switches, affective expression, and repetitive reinforcement. However, studies like Zhu (2018) warn against overuse, which may limit L2 optimization and introduce errors.

In the Philippine context, Metila (2019) emphasizes code-switching's communicative and socio-psychological functions, while research in Davao City highlights its role in language preference and identity expression (Demeterio Dreisbach 2017; Albino 2016). Despite its benefits, excessive code-switching may hinder full immersion in L2 learning, as noted by Macaro (2019).

1.3.2. Coping Mechanisms of Teachers in Employing Code-Switching—Teachers face the challenge of balancing the benefits and drawbacks of code-switching in the classroom. While it aids comprehension and inclusion, it can impede L2 acquisition and reinforce dependency on L1. Educators like De Castro et al. (2021) and Agna et al. (2022) stress the need to minimize code-switching and focus on immersive L2 environments to enhance proficiency. Encouraging L2 use through interactive and meaningful activities fosters better language skills and global citizenship (Loewen et al., 2019; Mercer Dörnyei, 2020). Effective communication, including judicious code-

switching, can build rapport and support comprehension, particularly in multilingual classrooms (Gort and Pontier, 2019).

However, reliance on code-switching can lead to negative perceptions and hinder L2 fluency (Pollard, 2020). To counter these effects, educators should receive professional development to strategically use code-switching, balancing its advantages with the goal of enhancing L2 proficiency (García Wei, 2020; Palmer et al., 2018).

1.3.3. Insights on the Experiences and Coping Mechanisms of Teachers for Code-Switching—Code-switching has emerged as a significant pedagogical tool in multilingual classrooms, facilitating understanding and validating students' linguistic identities. Research by García and Wei (2020) and Creese and Blackledge (2018) supports its role in bridging knowledge gaps and scaffolding instruction. However, effective use requires strategic planning and teacher training to ensure it enhances rather than hinders learning. The ongoing rise in multilingualism underscores the importance of code-switching in promoting inclusive and effective education.

1.4. Theoretical Lens—The theoretical underpinning of the study was anchored on the Theory of Code-Switching by Hoffman (1991). The theory states that there are seven reasons to switch languages, namely the need to talk about a particular topic, the necessity of quoting somebody else, being emphatic about something, the essential of using interjections, the need to use repetition for clarification, the necessity of intention in clarifying the speech context for interlocutor, and the need to express group identity. In the idea of language learning, this sociolinguistic phenomenon serves as a vital tool. For teachers, they must be equally aware that in some contexts one variety of language serves their needs better than another. The variety shows different styles of language that teachers use depending on where they are, who

they are talking to, and what kind of impression they want to communicate to their students. In this study, I relied on the Theory of Code-Switching in order to better understand the reasons why teachers employ code-switching in their classrooms. With respect to the focus of this study which is the code-switching of teachers in an ESL classroom. The theory encapsulates the reason why teachers employ code-switching and the benefits that they get from it. Although it is necessary to hone and mold students to become effective speakers of the target language, using their first language (L1) can be a scaffold for them to reach the tantamount of successful language learning. The study was further reinforced by Speech Accommodation Theory (SAT) by Giles and Powesland (1975) as cited by Boztepe (2003). The theory posits that speakers adjust their speech style as a way of expressing their attitudes or intentions toward their interlocutors. The two key concepts introduced by SAT are convergence and divergence. The former refers to accommodating the speech style of one's interlocutor, the latter signals a shift away from it. The notion of convergence is considered to convey a sense of solidarity. In contrast, divergence is a means to create social distance from one's interlocutor through which social disapproval is communicated. As applied in the context of the present study, the SAT theory explains how a speaker connects and adjusts their speech style depending on their attitude and intention. In this study, the speaker refers to the language teachers, while the interlocutors are considered the students in a language class. Teachers employ code-switching to connect with students through their L1 and help build rapport in the students' second language learning. Figure 1 presents the conceptual framework of the study. It shows three interconnected working themes. The Teacher's experiences of Employing Code-Switching in their Classroom, a qualitative inquiry that allows researchers, teachers, and learners to pro-

Fig. 1. Conceptual Framework of the Study

vide the necessary skills and knowledge and focus on engaging in meaningful inquiry about their professional practice, would enhance this practice. There was a genuine concern, as could be viewed with the first circle, which interlinks to the second circle; however, the center of the

two circles determines that there was a way coping mechanism of teachers in employing code-switching, and their intersection was the insights from the experiences and coping mechanisms of teachers.

2. Methodology

This chapter effectively addresses the study’s specific objectives by outlining the systematic procedures and methodologies used in phenomenological research. It also explains the selected research design and my roles as the researcher throughout the study’s implementation. Moreover, it offers thorough insights into the research subjects, clarifying their procedures and selection standards. The chapter concludes by exploring the data collection and analysis techniques and the strategies used to uphold ethical standards during the research. Artificial intelligence (AI) was used for proofreading, as it is a common ethical practice in many articles today.

2.1. Philosophical Assumptions—A study’s philosophical and qualitative presumptions were vital in steering the investigation. Four fundamental assumptions—ontological, epistemological, axiological, and methodological—form the bedrock for comprehending qualitative research. These assumptions establish the groundwork for the research design and inform the researcher’s approach to the study. A paradigm is a broad framework or perspective that guides and shapes how researchers approach their studies, formulate research questions, gather data, analyze findings, and interpret results. It encompasses

a set of beliefs, assumptions, methodologies, and theoretical foundations that influence how researchers conceptualize and conduct their research (Zukauskas et al., 2018). In this research, the paradigm guided the choice of methodology, methods, and techniques, shaping the overall research process and ensuring coherence in the study. Ontology. This study section focuses on the relationship between the problem and reality. Creswell (2013) asserts that the research participants’ perceptions of reality are varied and subjective. This study recognizes the complexity and diversity of the realities faced by secondary school English teachers regarding

code-switching in their classrooms. Teachers' stories add to a diverse yet collective understanding of their experiences. It was my sole responsibility to use theme analysis to capture these various realities and provide a thorough picture of teachers' experiences and coping strategies with code-switching.

Epistemology. Epistemology deals with the nature of knowledge and the relationship between the knower and the known. According to Guba and Lincoln, as referenced by Creswell (2013), the researcher tried to reduce the gap between them and the participants based on the epistemological premise. By engaging directly with the participants, I would become an "insider," facilitating a more authentic and nuanced data collection. This approach supports the gathering of firsthand experiences and coping mechanisms, which were critical in exploring the participants' subjective realities.

Axiology. It concerns the influence and importance of my values as a researcher in this study. According to Creswell (2013), acknowledging and openly discussing the researcher's values that shape the study was crucial. The values which influence how data are interpreted and presented were explicitly acknowledged in the research process. As a researcher, I would handle each participant's narrative with care and integrity and always have the utmost respect for the information they provide. This commitment guarantees that the teachers' experiences are communicated truthfully, mirroring their individual and research values.

Methodology. According to Crotty (2020), this was "the strategy, plan of action, process, or design lying behind the choice and use of particular methods and linking the choice and use of the methods to the desired outcomes." Its objectives are to explain, assess, and defend procedures (Wellington, 2015). This study used a qualitative methodology to explore the experiences and coping mechanisms of secondary school English teachers about code-switching. In order to support the ontological and episte-

mological tenets, specific techniques like focus groups and interviews are employed, enabling a thorough and sympathetic examination of participants' stories. These techniques were chosen because they can successfully convey the complexity and depth of the participants' experiences.

Rhetoric. In research, rhetoric was the skillful and convincing use of language, communication strategies, and presentation tactics to effectively communicate concepts, claims, and conclusions to sway the audience's opinion and comprehension of the study (Beqiri, 2018). I plan to utilize an engaging and respectful narrative style that honors the participants' voices while effectively communicating the significance of the findings. This method not only makes the research more accessible to read but also guarantees that the interpretations are strong and based on the participants' experiences.

2.2. Qualitative Assumptions—Using a phenomenological research methodology, I aimed to explore the experiences and coping mechanisms of secondary school English teachers from Davao City. I aimed to gather information about their experiences, coping mechanisms, and insights about the phenomenon I was studying. Utilizing phenomenology as my guiding qualitative framework, I sought to uncover the essence and significance of the roles played by these individuals, emphasizing their unique viewpoints and the intricate details of their experiences. As the study's qualitative researcher, I support a level of investigation beyond cursory observations. My research aims to investigate participants' experiences and coping mechanisms concerning the phenomenon. I emphasized the significance of understanding the complexities of the human experience in light of the various perspectives shaped by unique contexts, backgrounds, and personal histories (Neubauer et al., 2019). My study strongly emphasizes in-depth interviews, reflective dialogues, and the analysis of participants' nar-

ratives to capture the profound and complex nature of code-switching. I hope to contribute a thorough and contextually rich understanding of the challenges, coping mechanisms, and educational management insights related to code-switching while upholding phenomenological principles.

2.3. *Design and Procedure*—Determining the precise approach used in a study was crucial to customize the best research design, data collection strategy, and data analysis approach to the study's objectives. I used a qualitative research design in this investigation. Hammersley (2013) states that verbal rather than statistical analysis studies were appropriate for qualitative research. Since I would be studying the lived experiences, coping strategies, and insights of secondary school English teachers about code-switching. The qualitative design was the most appropriate. This means that I describe and elaborate on this phenomenon rather than establishing or refuting theories. There are, however, specialized methods used in qualitative research, including grounded theory, narrative, case studies, phenomenology, and ethnography. Using a qualitative phenomenological research design, I explored the lived experiences of the participants in this particular setting. I selected this approach because, according to Asper's (2009) work, the scientific side of phenomenological research focuses on communicating the viewpoints of the subjects and the importance of their experiences, then applying scientific concepts to analyze these perspectives. Furthermore, according to Creswell (2018), a phenomenological study was a method of inquiry that describes the complex and collective experiences of the participants with respect to a particular phenomenon. A key idea in phenomenology was to reduce one's interpretations of a particular phenomenon to a description that could be applied to all situations. Therefore, my goal is to identify a phenomenon that revolves around the participants' experience of code-switching. I

collected information from people who have direct experience with this phenomenon in order to create detailed and accurate descriptions.

2.4. *Research Participants*—Qualitative analyses typically require a smaller sample size than quantitative analyses. Qualitative sample sizes should be large enough to obtain feedback for most perceptions. Obtaining most or all the perceptions leads to the attainment of saturation. Saturation occurs when more participants are added to the study, which does not result in additional perspectives or information. Glaser and Strauss (2017) recommend the concept of saturation for achieving an appropriate sample size in qualitative studies. For phenomenological studies, Creswell (1998) recommends 5 to twenty-five. There are no specific rules when determining the appropriate sample size in qualitative research. Qualitative sample size may best be determined by the time allotted, resources available, and study objectives (Patton, 2002). The participants in this study consisted of 10 secondary high school English teachers from schools in Buhangin District. Five participants were for the In-Depth Interview and another five for the Focus Group Discussion. By equally distributing the participants, I was able to gather more diverse and varied responses from them. These participants were selected based on specific criteria: they are grade-9 teachers currently handling an English subject, have the same L1 with their students, employ code-switching in the classroom, and were willing to participate in the study. I utilized the purposive sampling design, which was also known as judgmental, selective, or subjective sampling. The participants were chosen based on the criteria or purpose of the study (Creswell, 2013). This method ensured that the findings would be authentic (Marshall, 1996).

2.5. *Ethical Considerations*—Ethical considerations were crucial because they relate to the moral principles and guidelines that govern my conduct as a researcher. These princi-

ples ensure that I carry out my investigations responsibly, treating participants respectfully and striving to generate reliable and precise information. To protect participants, maintain scientific integrity, and foster trust within the research community, I adhere to established ethical standards in my research practices (Resnik, 2020).

Social value. This concerns the potential benefits and favorable outcomes that research can bring to society, like addressing problems or improving people's quality of life. I evaluate the societal value of my study by acknowledging its potential impact and importance for the larger community. This ensures that resources are directed toward research that has the potential to create significant advantages for society.

Informed Consent. This involves obtaining a participant's voluntary agreement to participate in a research study in which they have been provided sufficient information about the study's purpose, methods, potential drawbacks, and benefits. In this research involving teachers, I was responsible for ensuring that the participants fully understood the study and their rights. This dual layer of explanation allowed them to make an informed decision about participation, thereby preserving the students' autonomy and dignity and ensuring parental consent.

Vulnerability. The vulnerability of research participants, especially teachers, pertains to their increased risk of experiencing harm, exploitation, or coercion due to factors such as age, cognitive ability, or socioeconomic status. As a researcher, I needed to acknowledge and consider the potential vulnerability of these participants and take appropriate measures to protect them. This involves providing additional safeguards and support, such as obtaining informed consent from participants, ensuring confidentiality, and carefully explaining their rights and the study's procedures in a way they can understand. Additionally, I modified research methods to minimize potential adverse effects, ensuring that the well-being of these students was prioritized throughout the study.

Risks, benefits, and safety. In research, it was essential to carefully evaluate the potential risks and benefits associated with participation in a study and implement measures that safeguard the well-being of participants. These elements involve assessing the potential disadvantages and advantages of participating in a study, along with establishing strategies to ensure the welfare of participants. In this investigation, as the researcher, I meticulously assess and balance these factors, ensuring that the potential benefits outweigh the risks. I put adequate precautions in place to minimize harm while optimizing participants' safety, particularly considering student participants' vulnerabilities. This comprehensive approach is crucial to maintaining ethical standards and protecting the participants throughout the research process.

Privacy and confidentiality. Privacy and confidentiality in research are about safeguarding participants' personal information and ensuring their identity remains confidential unless they explicitly consent to disclosure. In the context of this study, I am responsible for implementing appropriate protocols to secure participants' data and maintain confidentiality. This includes anonymizing data, securely storing information, and limiting access to authorized personnel only. These measures were crucial to protecting student participants' privacy and upholding the research process's integrity.

Justice. This concept relates to the equitable allocation of the advantages and disadvantages of research across various segments of society. In this study, I ensured that my research was inclusive, avoiding exploiting or excluding vulnerable groups. Additionally, I strive to make the research's benefits accessible to all who could benefit from it. This approach promotes fairness and equity throughout the research process, ensuring that no group bears an undue burden or is left out of the potential gains from the findings.

Transparency. Transparency in research encompasses maintaining integrity at every phase of the study, from its conception

and execution to reporting results. I offer clear and truthful information regarding my research methodologies and outcomes in this study. Furthermore, I am receptive to examination and feedback. Transparency acts as a catalyst for trust, credibility, and accountability, not only within the research community but also among the general public. This commitment to openness ensures that the process and results of my research are accessible and understandable to all stakeholders involved. The qualification of a researcher. The qualification of a researcher relates to one's academic background, professional experience, and proficiency in a particular area of study, ensuring that one possesses the requisite abilities and knowledge to conduct the research competently. In this investigation, I hold suitable qualifications that showcase my capability to conduct research, analyze data, and interpret the results. My expertise and training provide the foundation to approach this study with a rigorous scientific method and critical analytical skills, ensuring the integrity and validity of the findings. The adequacy of facilities. This addresses the presence and suitability of the essential resources, tools, and infrastructure required to execute a study efficiently and securely. In this research, I guarantee access to appropriate investigation facilities. This access facilitates the creation of credible and consistent findings and mitigates potential risks to study participants. Having the right facilities ensures that the data collection and analysis processes are conducted under conditions that uphold the highest research integrity and safety standards. Community involvement. This encompasses the dynamic involvement and active engagement of community members, stakeholders, or the intended study population throughout the research journey, from initial planning to sharing research outcomes. In this study, I engage the community to guarantee the study's relevance, acceptability, and potential impact. Additionally, this involvement fosters trust and

cooperation between me and the community. Engaging with the community not only helps to tailor the research to be more effective and meaningful but also enhances the overall quality and applicability of the results. Plagiarism and fabrication. Researchers should strictly follow principles of academic honesty and integrity. This entails giving proper credit to the work of others, presenting original contributions, and verifying the accuracy and authenticity of data. In this study, I employed tools like plagiarism detectors. I maintained thorough documentation of my research procedures to ensure that my work was devoid of plagiarism and that all data and discoveries were authentic and reliable. By upholding these principles, I enhance the credibility and trustworthiness of the research community.

2.6. Role of the Researcher—As an unbiased research facilitator and promoter, I ensured the research process was conducted fairly, objectively, and without personal bias, prejudice, or influence from outside sources. I create an environment that encourages the open and honest exploration of ideas and promotes fairness in data collection and analysis. This commitment to impartiality helps to uphold the integrity of the research process and ensures that the findings are reliable and representative of the phenomena being studied. As an expert in qualitative methods, I am familiar with various qualitative research techniques, such as interviews, focus groups, and participant observation. I possess the skills and knowledge necessary to design, conduct, and analyze qualitative studies, ensuring that the research question was satisfactorily addressed and the results were legitimate and dependable. My expertise in these methods allows me to deeply explore complex social phenomena and capture the nuanced experiences of participants, contributing to the validity and reliability of the research findings. As a data collector and keeper, I gather information from various sources, such as interviews or obser-

vations, ensuring accurate and secure storage. I followed ethical guidelines, safeguarded participants' privacy, and ensured that data was structured and available for later examination and understanding. This careful management of data helps maintain the integrity of the research process. It supports producing credible, reliable findings that can be reviewed and utilized by others in the academic community. As a data analyst, I analyze the gathered data to discover trends, patterns, and valuable perspectives under the research query. I utilize meticulous qualitative data analysis methods like coding and thematic analysis to extract significant findings and enrich the knowledge base within my discipline. This approach allows me to deeply understand the data, providing insights that were not only relevant but also contribute significantly to the field, enhancing scholarly discussions and practical applications related to the study topic. Finally, as an organizer and presenter of data, I am tasked with synthesizing and communicating the research findings concisely and coherently. This entails skillfully conveying the study's objectives, approaches, outcomes, and ramifications through written documents, presentations, or alternative means of transmitting information. I ensure the research results are easily accessible and comprehensible to the designated audience. This approach helps to maximize the impact of the findings, ensuring they are not only shared but also understood and utilized by others in ways that can further knowledge and influence practice in the field.

2.7. Data Collection—This study employed a systematic data collection procedure. Several steps were taken to adhere to the proper data collection procedure, ensuring the data collection's accuracy and objectivity. The following is the step-by-step process of gathering the data needed. Securing endorsement from the Dean of Graduate School, the Schools Division Superintendent, and the School Principal. To initiate the data collection process, I secure en-

dorsements from key stakeholders, including the Dean of the Graduate School, the Schools Division Superintendent, the School Principal, and the participants' parents. This process involves submitting formal letters outlining the research objectives and methodology, accompanied by any supporting documents. This crucial step was scheduled to occur within the last two weeks of May 2024, ensuring that all necessary permissions were in place before data collection. This proactive approach facilitates compliance with ethical standards and fosters a cooperative environment among all parties involved. I am asking permission from the Schools Division Superintendent. Upon receiving the endorsement, I requested permission from the school's division superintendent. This requires submitting a formal letter detailing the research proposal and its significance to the educational community. Along with the letter, I attached Chapters 1 and 2 of my dissertation and the research instrument, clearly explaining the study's objectives and participant identification process. Moreover, I waited for the response from the Schools Division Superintendent (SDS) before proceeding with the data collection. This step was undertaken during the second week of January 2024, ensuring that all necessary approvals were in place to conduct the research ethically and effectively. I was asking for permission from the school heads. Once permission was granted, I sought approval from the school heads of the selected institutions. This step involves submitting formal request letters to each school head, outlining the research's purpose and the expected data collection timeframe. I asked permission to conduct the study from the third week of March 2024. Obtaining consent from the participants. With the school heads' approval, I asked for consent from the research participants, who were teachers. These forms clearly explain the research purpose, participant rights, and confidentiality measures. This consent process ensures that

the teachers were fully informed and agree to participate. Asking for consent from both the participants and their parents or guardians was done in the last week of March 2024. Conducting the interview. Upon securing consent from all participants, I would schedule and conduct the interviews using a structured or semi-structured interview guide to ensure consistency and reliability in data collection. The interviews took place in the first two weeks of April 2024. Transcribing the interviewees' responses. Following the interview sessions, I would meticulously transcribe the interviewees' remarks, taking diligent account of non-verbal cues and contextually relevant details. This procedure would use audio recordings and field notes to capture the breadth of participants' reactions comprehensively. The transcription of interviewee responses was scheduled for the third week of April 2024.

2.8. *Data Analysis*—After collecting the data, I began data coding and thematic content analysis. This involves methodically structuring the transcribed data into categories, subcategories, and themes from the interview dialogues. By discerning patterns and connections within the data, I formulate conclusions and glean insights directly related to the research objectives. This process allows me to interpret the data effectively, ensuring that the findings accurately reflect the participants' experiences and perspectives. In this study, I employed Creswell's Thematic Analysis approach, which was particularly suited for encompassing a range of perspectives and portrayals in participants' feedback. Adopting thematic analysis authenticates the portrayal of individual components and facilitates categorizing identified patterns within the provided responses. Thematic analysis was a qualitative research technique used to recognize, scrutinize, and interpret patterns or themes present within qualitative data in textual, visual, or other formats. As a qualitative research approach, thematic analysis allows researchers to

arrange and dissect complex data sets systematically. It involves searching for overarching themes that encapsulate the narratives embedded within the data. This process necessitates the identification of themes through meticulous examination and repeated review of transcribed data (Dawadi, 2020). This methodical approach helped ensure the analysis was comprehensive and reflective of the data collected, providing deep insights into the study's objectives. Therefore, my research used Creswell's Thematic Analysis, necessitating extensive theming and transcript interpretation. According to Caulfield (2020), there were multiple essential phases in Creswell's Thematic Analysis, including familiarization, coding, generating themes, reviewing themes, defining and labeling themes, and writing up. I become fully immersed in the intricacies and subtleties of the content as I become acquainted with the data to begin this process. After that, I start categorizing the data using semantic richness to group different informational components. I create themes that encapsulate the main ideas of the data using these codes. After that, these themes are examined and improved to ensure they appropriately depict the dataset. Every theme has a definition and name that elucidates the fundamental ideas. The last step combines the themes and insights into a cohesive article that conveys the study's conclusions. This methodical approach guarantees a comprehensive examination and enhances the comprehension of the information.

2.9. *Trustworthiness of the Study*—The trustworthiness of a study was about how reliable, sensible, and authentic the research results were, ensuring that the conclusions were trustworthy and accurate. In qualitative research, factors like credibility, transferability, confirmability, and dependability are often used to evaluate the study's reliability. According to Guba (1981), these considerations were further described below. Credibility. Building credibility entails proving that the results were accurate.

Credibility was essential for this study because it evaluates if the results accurately represent the realities and experiences of sophomore students participating in extra-curricular activities. I converse with the participants for a long time to gain a thorough understanding of their experiences and increase my credibility. I also use triangulation, gathering information from various sources, including observations, interviews, and questionnaires. In order to confirm the interpretations, I gave the teachers a preliminary version of the findings as part of member checking. Transferability. The degree to which the results of this study could be used in different situations or with different populations is referred to as transferability. While the particular insights were closely linked to secondary high school English teachers' experiences in a specific educational environment, I would thoroughly explain the research context and methodology. The study's transferability was increased because this thorough, rich narrative enables others, including educators, school administrators, and researchers, to assess how well the results apply to comparable contexts or populations. Confirmability. Confirmability deals with the study's objectivity by ensuring that the respondents, not my prejudices or biases, shaped the findings. I keep a thorough audit trail detailing every step of the research process, from data collection to data analysis decisions, to ensure confirmability. This methodological transparency makes it possible for other researchers to evaluate the research's objectivity by following the study's development and reviewing the choices made. Dependability. Dependability means proving that the study results were reliable and repeatable in similar situations. This study's dependability was attained through meticulous documentation of the entire research procedure, including the methods used for data collection and analysis. By ensuring that other researchers could duplicate the study and possibly produce consistent results,

such documentation validates the research's dependability. By following these standards, the research not only offers valid and trustworthy conclusions regarding the effects of extracurricular activities on sophomore students but also offers a framework that researchers and other educators can use to compare similar learning environments. This methodology enhances the study's standing in the academic community and provides insightful information for upcoming studies and instructional design.

2.10. Analytical Framework—The analytical framework in phenomenological research was a methodical and structured approach to data analysis, interpretation, and presentation. In this research study, I used Colaizzi's method to analyze data from the interviews and discussions with the participants regarding their lived experiences with code-switching. According to Morrow et al. (2021), Colaizzi's (1978) method features a distinctive seven-step process offering rigorous analysis, closely adhering to the data at each stage. This method culminates in a concise yet comprehensive description of the phenomenon under study, validated by the participants who experienced it. The effectiveness of this approach relies on rich first-person accounts of experiences, which can be collected through various means. Although face-to-face interviews are common, data could also be gathered from written narratives, blogs, research diaries, online interviews, and other forms. This method enables researchers to uncover emergent themes and explore their intricate relationships (Wirihana et al., 2018). Data Familiarization. By reading and rereading the transcripts several times, I aim to fully understand the meanings conveyed by the participants and gain a global sense of the phenomenon being studied. This thorough review process was crucial for fully grasping the nuances of participants' statements, enabling a deeper analysis of their experiences. Identifying Significant Statements. I carefully identify every statement in the nar-

ratives directly related to the phenomenon I am studying. To identify and highlight phrases and descriptions that shed light on the particular experiences under study, a thorough examination of the gathered data—such as written narratives or transcripts of interviews—must be conducted. This step is essential to ensuring that my analysis stays on topic and provides a strong basis for future thematic development. **Formulating Meanings.** After carefully examining the critical statements, I determined meanings that were pertinent to the phenomenon. Although Colaizzi admits that complete bracketing was never possible, I have to reflexively “bracket” my presuppositions to stick closely to the phenomenon as experienced. To guarantee that the analysis stays rooted in the participants’ actual experiences, this process entails putting aside my interpretations as much as practical. **Clustering Themes.** I ensure a rigorous analysis that remains true to the participants’ experiences by grouping the identified meanings into themes shared by all accounts. Throughout this process, presuppositions must be bracketed, mainly to avoid any possible influence from existing theories. Allowing the themes to naturally arise from the data rather than being influenced by outside forces preserves the integrity of the analysis. I am developing an exhaustive description. I incorporate every theme generated in

the previous step into a comprehensive and all-encompassing description of the phenomenon I write. By identifying common themes from the participant accounts, this thorough description seeks to convey the essence and complexity of the phenomenon. This step ensures that the final representation presents a comprehensive perspective of each participant’s experiences. I am producing the fundamental structure. I break down the lengthy explanation into a succinct statement highlighting the key elements that I believe are crucial to understanding the phenomenon’s structure. This succinct synthesis effectively and concisely communicates the essence of the participants’ experiences, concentrating on the essential components necessary for comprehending the phenomenon. I am seeking verification of the fundamental structure. I ask participants if the fundamental structure statement accurately reflects their experience by returning it to all participants or, in more extensive studies, to a subsample. I might go back and change the earlier stages of the analysis in light of their comments. Through this iterative process, the validity and credibility of the findings were increased, and the analysis was firmly based on the participants’ perspectives. The following figure illustrates this rigorous process, highlighting each step to comprehensively explain the actions taken to analyze the data.

3. Results and Discussion

This part of the study dealt with the research questions and the answers extracted from the participants’ responses. The secondary English teachers who employed code-switching in their EFL classroom put open their experiences and coping mechanisms they experienced upon utilizing the said sociolinguistic phenomenon. There were four emerging themes for lived experiences: repetitive function, affective function, impeding the student’s learning of L2, and decline in students’ language proficiency and confidence. Meanwhile, three themes have been unfurled for coping mechanisms: effective communication, minimizing code-switching, and encouraging the utilization of L2. Lastly, the insights were code-switching as an emerging language pedagogy, applying the proper function of code-switching, and a bridge from the known to the unknown.

Fig. 2. Analytical Framework of the Study

3.1. *Experiences of Teachers in the Employment Of Code-Switching in their Classroom*—Language learning is often called crossing the bridge from the known to the unknown. It has earned that definition simply because one cannot learn and understand a language if one does not know two languages. Included in those two languages is your first language or L1. In an English as a Second Language (ESL) classroom, teachers tend to motivate and encourage their students to speak and utilize the target language; however, more often than not, teachers find themselves unconsciously employing the first language for various reasons. Code-switching happens more than we notice, but this sociolinguistic phenomenon has earned praise and criticism. The following emerging themes are the perceptions of the benefits of code-switching under the secondary English teachers’ lens.

3.1.1. *Code-switching’s repetitive function*—True to the famous adage that one cannot strike perfection on their first try. The same applies in an EFL classroom; learners take some time to get better and become acquainted with

the target language, which, in this case, is English. Since the language they are learning is entirely different from their first language, they require time to adjust. Hence, code-switching helped them adjust. Participants expressed how it aided them in making the students understand the classroom instruction better and more transparently.

The responses of the abovementioned participants shared the same thoughts about code-switching in the classroom. According to them, code-switching aids in clarifying classroom instructions and improving the atmosphere. Aside from that, code-switching also helps eliminate shame. Instead, code-switching promotes learning the target language among the students. On the same thread, Sondang and Bonik (2017) have argued that in the English as a Second Language (ESL) classroom context, code-switching helps assist English learners’ teaching and learning process. It also helps low-proficiency students gain better comprehension, especially when given classroom procedures. Teachers need to consider this a careful strategy. The

author's point mentioned above echoes the sentiments of IDI 2. The participants shared that the students are still novices and recognize that learning a new language can be intimidating. In short, some students have difficulty processing the lesson when delivered in the target language. Hence, code-switching helps deliver instruction across the classroom. In addition, Hoffman's (1991) Theory of Code-Switching postulates reasons why people commit code-switching. One of the seven reasons under the theory's umbrella is the repetition of clarification. This coincides with the narratives of IDI 1, IDI 2, and IDI 3. The repetitive function of code-switching has allowed better clarification among the students. The participants in the focus group discussion shared the same views and opinions as the participants in the in-depth interview. IDI 6 has shared how code-switching's repetitive function can help students understand it. Meanwhile, FGD 7 focuses on the students' vocabulary and translation to enhance students' understanding. FGD 8 is on the same page as FGD 7, and they clarify meaning by translating difficult words they use in class. The responses are connected to Hoffman's Theory of Code-Switching (1991). One of the seven reasons the proponent postulated is the need to discuss a particular topic. In this case, FGD 7 and FGD 8 translate the problematic words they encounter. These problematic words are essential in elevating students' understanding; hence, they must be translated to present students with a more relatable word they can easily comprehend. Furthermore, corroborating the participants' perception of code-switching, authors Mattson and Burenhult (1999, as cited from Shafi, Kazmi, and Asif, 2019), that code-switching plays a repetitive function in the classroom. Teachers use code-switching to transfer the necessary knowledge to the student for clarity. An example of code-switching's repetitive function is when a teacher gives instruction in a second language and code-switches to the native

language to clarify meaning. In this way, the teacher stresses the importance of the second language content for efficient comprehension. On the same line of thought, Iytoglu (2015) also claims that using the first language may save time compared to using only the target language. He also added that using students' L1 may be encouraged to provide more remarkable input for the learner. He pointed out that one of the functions of teachers' code-switching is facilitating understanding of grammatical structures and rules. This explains a situation where a teacher changes his/her language according to the topic under discussion. Meanwhile, Shafi, Kazim, and Asif (2019) carried out a study among Portuguese-speaking university students who were learning. They have also pointed out that the teacher changes his/her language to the student's native language in dealing with specific grammar points taught at that moment. The study's findings further revealed that the teacher switched codes from a second to a first language to clarify their understanding of grammatical structure. This led the learners to reflect on the form under analysis and facilitated their understanding. Like the participants' responses, they code-switch from the first language to the target language, English, for clarification and to give meaning to complex vocabulary. Consequently, Abad (2020) found that code-switching is particularly helpful in simplifying the meaning of difficult words or abstract concepts to the learners' level of competence and experience. The speech mode has also created a low-anxiety classroom atmosphere conducive to learning.

3.1.2. Affective function—The second emerging theme gathered from the participants' responses is code-switching's affective function inside the classroom. Students may find speaking and communicating using a second language intimidating. Hence, code-switching helps the students be at ease and comfortable slowly and gradually. It is important to note that participants stated that the affective function of code-

switching fosters a cheerful learning ambiance.

The participants' responses in the in-depth interview focus on the affective function or aspect of committing code-switching in the classroom. IDI 2 has shared that she utilizes Bisaya in her classroom so students can grasp the lesson and be more participative. Meanwhile, IDI 3 mentioned the importance of a nourishing environment and a healthy classroom atmosphere. Not only does it allow students to learn better, but they would also be able to take an active part and role in the teaching and learning process. IDI 5 also emphasizes the students' emotions during the learning process. The narratives shared by the participants align with Zabrodjkaja's (2017) concept that teachers code-switch to foster connections among students. According to this idea, a teacher's use of the first language (L1) can help build a strong bond among students, making them feel more at ease in the learning environment. This underscores the importance of linguistic diversity in the classroom and its role in creating a comfortable and inclusive learning space. Meanwhile, it is anchored on the Speech Accommodation Theory by Giles and Powesland (1975, as cited from Boztepe, 2003). This theory focuses on the speaker and the interlocutors. It further postulates that speakers adjust their speech style to express their attitudes and intentions toward the interlocutors. In this case, the teachers are the speakers, and the students are the interlocutors. The speaker's (teacher) attitude and intentions can affect how the interlocutors (students) perceive the message. The focus group discussion shares the same theme with the in-depth interview. The emerging theme is an affective function that code-switching plays inside the classroom. Converging studies have also uncovered the affective function that code-switching plays in a language learning classroom. According to Mattson and Burenhult (1999, as cited from Shafi, Kazmi, and Asif, 2019), code-switching contributes to creating a supportive

language environment in the classroom. It is in line with the thoughts shared by FGD 7 and 9, for she mentioned that it is significant that students feel safe and comfortable while learning in a conducive learning atmosphere. Moreover, Metila (2019) also revealed the same findings in her study of the Philippine scene. Her study on code-switching stated that it fosters a cheerful learning ambiance. It is also considered a simplification strategy that students with poor English and Filipino proficiency have been observed to use since it transforms the mood of the classroom from formal to informal. Additionally, the affective function expresses emotions. Teachers utilize it to build solidarity and intimate relations with students. On the same page, Zabrodjkaja (2017) added another function of code-switching in the classroom, and that is to create a supportive language learning environment. Teacher shifts codes or language to build a connection or relationship among the students. Using the first language (L1) helps a teacher create a close relationship among the students which can help them be comfortable while learning. A comfortable atmosphere can be created through the application of humor. The shifting of codes can also be used for praising or telling the students. These factors contribute to the overall supportive environment of a language classroom. Meanwhile, Hoffman's Theory of Code-Switching (1991) postulates that teachers or speakers must be equally aware of the context to see which variety of language will serve better than the other. It is important that a teacher considers the students' ability before code-switching to provide them with the appropriate support. Once they feel comfortable and safe, successful language learning follows.

3.1.3. Impede the students' learning of a second language (L2)—The participants have perceived code-switching as impeding the students' learning of the second language, which in this case is English. They noted that excessive code-switching in the classroom pre-

vents students from becoming fluent in the target language. The participants' responses in the in-depth interview are in line with the ideas of Jamshidi and Navehabriam (2013). In their study, they mentioned that although code-switching appears to be a natural and practical strategy for bilingual and multilingual educators and students, it is important to recognize its drawbacks. Moreover, the same author further explained that code-switching has a tendency to obstruct language development, inhibit language separation, and promote linguistic inequities. They also added that code-switching may prevent students from becoming fluent in their target language, eventually harming their chances of success in school and the workforce. The responses also coincide with the findings of Dykhanova (2015). The research examined the purpose of code-switching in the classroom and the attitude of teachers and students towards it. He further concluded that code-switching did nothing to improve the student's language skills. Teachers also utilize code-switching primarily for translation or interpretation needs. Meanwhile, in connection with the theory on which this study was anchored, Hoffman's Theory of Code-Switching (1991) presented seven reasons why we commit code-switching. Dykhanova (2015) mentions one reason: repetition for clarity. However, the theory states that one must be equally aware of the context of the situation before switching from one language to another.

In this part, the responses of the participants in the focus group discussion were focused on the tendency of code-switching to impede the language learning of the students. FGD 8 stated that it all depends on how the teacher employs code-switching in the classroom. It can be advantageous or disadvantageous depending on how it is applied. Meanwhile, FGD 9 clarifies that code-switching should only function as an aid in the classroom and should not be utilized all the time. Since it is a language learning class, the students should develop mastery

and fluency of the target language. FGD 10 agreed with FGD 9 and stated that it has the potential to hold back the students' language learning development. Meanwhile, as Hoffman (1991) states in his theory about code-switching, the teacher should be equally aware of utilizing code-switching at the right time and for the right purpose. It is a vital tool, hence it should be used and employed responsibly. In the same vein, Dylkhanova (2015) examined the purposes of code-switching and attitudes toward it, both teachers and students have a generally negative opinion of this behavior. With the underlying assumption that code-switching did nothing to improve students' language skill levels, teachers frequently used code-switching primarily for translation and interpretation needs. Moreover, a substantial portion of educators and practitioners in the field of English Language Teaching (ELT) concur that code-switching is improper and unacceptable in a classroom setting. They support a strong distinction between the use of the target or second language (L2) and the native language (L1), as mentioned by Cummins (2005). This perspective claims that code-switching, especially to the L1 might impede language learning.

3.1.4. The decline in language proficiency and confidence of students—Notably, participants also highlighted the negative effect code-switching may have on students, especially their language proficiency and confidence in using the target language. Hence, another setback they shared is code-switching causing a decline in the language proficiency and confidence of the students. The participants' concerns in the in-depth interview are in line with the setbacks that code-switching might pose for the students and their language-learning process. IDI 2, IDI 3, and IDI 4 are all worried regarding the effect of code-switching on their students' fluency. Several authors also expressed the same perception as found in the study's findings. Sawir's (2005) findings also suggest that the lack of

fluency among international students can be attributed to the teacher using the students' first language (L1) in the classroom, highlighting a potential drawback of code-switching and bilingual methods in ESL education. In the same light, Hoffman (1999) postulated in his theory that code-switching serves for a variety of reasons. However, these reasons should be coupled with an adequate purpose so that code-switching would be helpful and would not impede or limit the students' fluency. In the focus group discussion, the emerging theme was emphasized by the participants. FGD 6 and FGD 8 share the same thought. They shared that code-switching has a tendency to hamper the students' language learning. It could have an effect on the lesson objective and goals that are set beforehand. Meanwhile, FGD 6 and FGD 9 stated that aside from the students' fluency, code-switching can also have an impact on the students' confidence in using the target language. Aside from impeding learning of the second language, code-switching also affects students' language proficiency. According to several academic studies, the use of code-switching in the classroom has been linked to significant negative effects on students' language proficiency and learning, as well as the potential for the formation of bad linguistic habits. Even while code-switching is common, it is frequently seen negatively because it might make it more difficult to learn

Figure 3 shows teachers' experiences employing code-switching in their classrooms and the emergence of the four themes: Repetitive function, affective function, decline in language proficiency and confidence of students, communication, and Impede students learning of L2.

3.2. *Coping mechanisms of teachers in employing code-switching in their classroom*—As mentioned, the utilization of code-switching has received both praise and criticism. This resulted in various converging ideas and per-

and master the target language. Additionally, the widespread use of code-switching may eventually threaten the supremacy of traditional languages by fostering the establishment of irregular or harmful linguistic practices (Aagna et al., 2022). These worries were highlighted by a study participant who said that "relying on code-switching too much can have a detrimental effect on my learning process, leading to slower language acquisition progress and a higher likelihood of achieving lower language proficiency." The participants' comments imply that code-switching presents barriers to learners' English language acquisition, especially in terms of their proficiency in English. Moreover, numerous studies have also illuminated the potential adverse effects of code-switching within English as a Second Language (ESL) classrooms. Aljoundi (2013) and Mokgwathi and Webb (2013) have both highlighted that the utilization of code-switching may lead to a deficiency in the English language proficiency among students and a decline in their confidence when speaking English. They also asserted that code-switching hurts learners' English proficiency and confidence. Excessive dependence on code-switching is undesirable because it may cause students' proficiency in their second language (L2) to drop, as well as their confidence levels.

ceptions on the real function and purpose of code-switching. When it is deemed appropriate to use and when it is impeding the students' language learning. The following recurring themes have been gathered from the scrutiny of the participant's responses in the in-depth interview and focus group discussion.

3.2.1. *Effective communication*—Based on the participants' perception, code-switching allows for a clear exchange of thoughts between students and teachers in the classroom. Also, it

Fig. 3. Experiences of Teachers in Employing Code-Switching in their Classroom

fosters classroom communication and has been observed to increase student participation. The participants' responses in the in-depth interview illuminate another theme related to the function of code-switching. According to IDI 3, IDI 4, and IDI 5, effective communication occurs when code-switching is employed and allowed in the classroom. To support the theme, Cook (2012) believes that code-switching is natural in a language classroom, and teachers should not discourage students from using it. He also argued that maximizing a second language (L2) in the classroom does not mean that L1 should be avoided altogether. This thought is in line with teachers' perception, for they do not enforce the utilization of L2 hence they allow the students to use L1 still in order for them to adjust. Corroborating the emerging theme is Hoffman's Theory of Code-switching (1991). The theory expresses the importance of tackling an important topic yet being limited by language. Hence, one of the reasons stipulated in the theory is the need to talk about a particular topic. Effective communication may occur

when what needs to be discussed is put into the open and when students are allowed to express their thoughts completely in a language they are comfortable using. Meanwhile, in the focus group discussion, participants shared the same thoughts about the benefits of code-switching in an EFL classroom.

The emerging theme from the in-depth interview was the same as that of the focus group discussion. Participants in the focus group discussion, such as FDG 6 and FDG 9, further emphasized the importance of code-switching in fostering effective communication inside the classroom. Meanwhile, FGD 7 mentions how code-switching helps students make adjustments when learning a new language. In the same line of thought, Bergsleithner (2018) took the students' perspective and found that they used code-switching to express themselves better, and code-switching is employed for understanding grammar topics. This holds a stronghold among studies that reveal the affirmative side of code-switching. It proves that the students realize the positive impact of this

emerging teaching pedagogy. Code-switching is for establishing effective communication. For Iyitoglu (2019), most of the time, it is the teaching method that should be adjusted and not the language of instruction, and the most crucial question is how appropriately the first language is used and how it can be used to foster the learning of a second language. However, on the flip side, many people in the language teaching community still have reservations about using the learners' L1 or code-switching in classrooms, objecting to it because it limits exposure to the target language and keeps students thinking in their L1. The use of code-switching in EFL classrooms has been a subject of controversy. It has been regarded as negative and undesirable behavior with a failure to use the target language.

3.2.2. *Encourages the utilization of L2—*

In a language learning classroom, a teacher inevitably switches from one language to another, especially if he/she is doing it for emphasis. As one of their shared experiences, frequent code-switching may impede the student's learning of their L2. Hence, they have shared in the interviews that they encourage the students to utilize the L2 whenever they speak or participate in class. What the participants have shared highlighted the importance of encouraging the students to utilize their L2. Even though code-switching is not prohibited, the participants emphasized that students should use the language in the classroom. The findings are consistent with the idea of Loewen et al. (2019). Encouraging students to use a second language (L2) in the classroom is crucial for effective language acquisition. The classroom interaction in the target language significantly enhances learners' ability to process and produce L2. This interaction should be meaningful and contextually relevant, allowing students to practice L2 in real-life scenarios and improve their linguistic and communicative competence. Moreover, Mercer and Dörnyei (2020) highlight the role of a sup-

portive and motivating classroom atmosphere in fostering language use. When students feel encouraged and supported by their peers and teachers, they are likelier to take risks and engage in L2 communication. Integrating the L2 into various classroom activities can significantly boost students' confidence and willingness to participate. This can be achieved through collaborative activities such as group discussions, peer reviews, and project-based learning, which enhance language skills and build a sense of community and shared purpose.

The responses in the FGD are consistent with that of the IDI. The participants' narratives focused on how they encourage their students to utilize English. Using L2 in the classroom prepares students for global citizenship and enhances cultural competence. In a globalized world, proficiency in multiple languages is a valuable asset. Duff (2018) expressed that using L2 in educational settings helps students understand different cultural perspectives and develop intercultural communication skills. This preparation benefits academic and professional opportunities and fosters a more inclusive and empathetic worldview. Encouraging the use of L2 in diverse and meaningful contexts helps students appreciate the practical and cultural relevance of language learning. Corroborating the above assertion, Gkonou et al. (2020) stated that teachers play a pivotal role in promoting L2 usage through innovative and engaging teaching methods. Employing diverse pedagogical strategies such as task-based learning, role-playing, and multimedia resources can make L2 learning more dynamic and effective. Additionally, providing timely and constructive feedback helps students refine their language skills and builds their confidence. By creating an interactive and supportive learning environment, educators can motivate students to actively use and improve their L2, leading to better overall language proficiency.

3.2.3. *Minimizing code-switching*—Aside from encouraging students to use L2, teachers also minimize their use of code-switching in the classroom. In the previous sections, the participants shared how frequent code-switching may impact students' language learning, fluency, and confidence. The participants in the IDI have shared that minimizing the application of code-switching in the classroom would help avoid its negative effects. IDI 5 even states that it should be used in moderation. In the same light, Macaro (2019) expressed that reducing code-switching helps students develop better comprehension and communication skills in L2, as they are encouraged to think and express themselves within the linguistic framework of the target language. This immersion is critical for developing fluency and accuracy. Minimizing code-switching in the classroom is essential for fostering a more immersive language learning environment. Recent research emphasizes that consistent use of the target language (L2) enhances language proficiency by providing more opportunities for authentic practice. Similarly, García and Wei (2018) suggest employing strategies such as setting clear expectations for language use, providing ample visual and contextual support, and using scaffolding techniques to aid comprehension. These methods help students feel more comfortable and capable of using L2 exclusively. Additionally, incorporating regular routines and language-rich

activities can help establish a norm for using L2, making it the default classroom communication mode. Teachers can minimize code-switching by creating a supportive, structured classroom environment that prioritizes L2 use. The FGD has reaped the same findings from the IDI participants. They have put great emphasis on reducing code-switching in a language-learning classroom. This aligns with the idea of Sayer and Ben (2020), who highlighted the importance of task-based learning in helping minimize code-switching, where students complete meaningful tasks using L2, thus naturally reducing the need to switch to their native language. Role-playing, simulations, and collaborative projects also promote sustained L2 use. These activities require students to rely on their L2 skills to negotiate meaning and achieve their objectives, reinforcing their language abilities. Meanwhile, teachers, on the other hand, can model effective L2 use and provide consistent feedback to encourage students to stay within the target language. From the idea of Turnbull and Dailey-O'Cain (2020), teacher behavior greatly influences student language use. By consistently speaking L2 and gently correcting instances of code-switching, teachers can set a strong example and reinforce the importance of staying in the target language. Constructive feedback helps students become aware of their language use patterns and develop strategies to maintain L2 use, leading to more excellent language proficiency and confidence.

Figure 4 shows teachers' coping mechanisms for employing code-switching in their classroom and the emergence of the four themes: effective communication, affective function, the decline in language proficiency and confidence of students, minimization of code-switching, and encourages the utilization of L2.

3.3. *Insights Gained from The Experiences and Coping Mechanisms Employed by*

Secondary English Teachers—The study's purpose is to uncover teachers' perspectives regarding the employment of code-switching in EFL classrooms. The culminating part of the study focuses on what language learning insights can be gathered rooted in the first-hand experiences and perceptions of English teachers. The end goal of this paper is to illuminate all aspects of code-switching: advantages and disadvantages.

Fig. 4. Coping Mechanisms of Teachers in Employing Code-Switching in their Classroom

tages. Also, these insights guide how to utilize the mentioned language pedagogy.

3.3.1. *Code-switching as an emerging language pedagogy*—We are in an era where globalization is taking center stage in almost all human endeavors. The vanishing of divisions across countries and people has opened new doors or opportunities to one and all. Greatly influenced by globalization is the learning of a new language, in this case, English which is considered as a lingua franca. Others have also noted how useful it is to be competent and fluent in conversing in English. Therefore, language learning enters the picture and since then we have been trying to paint a greater picture for effective language learning to take place. Consequently, an insight gathered from this study is the view of teachers on the power of code-switching in enhancing students’ learning of their L2. The following lines are drawn from the statement of participants in the in-depth interview. As IDI 1 stated, code-switching should be used as an aid in language teaching. L1 or first language should not be dropped altogether

because it would help the students with their adjustment in learning the target language. Meanwhile, IDI 2 shared that code-switching is advantageous in this day and age. It will take us on different paths and would open new doors of greater possibilities and endless opportunities. However, it should not be employed excessively. This is a similar idea to IDI 3, which states that everything is good as long as it is done in moderation. Adding to the points made in the in-depth interview, the focus group discussion plucked some points from the participants’ statements. FGD 6 emphasized that code-switching should be employed or married with purpose. On the other hand, FGD 7 also mentioned the negative effect that code-switching might cause despite being considered a vital sociolinguistic phenomenon. He added that the negative impact of code-switching can be prevented when employed responsibly. FGD 8 also acknowledged the positive effect of code-switching. Teachers switch codes depending on the need of the lesson and the context of the situation. FGD 8 further added that code-switching

would not only aid the students' understanding but also the teachers in terms of clarifying meaning for the students. In the same vein, García and Wei (2020) emphasize that code-switching can bridge gaps in understanding by providing immediate clarification in a student's first language. This practice helps learners grasp complex concepts without the additional cognitive burden of decoding a second language. By allowing students to access content in a language they are comfortable with, educators can enhance both comprehension and retention of material, thus promoting a deeper understanding of the subject matter. This method, supported by research from Creese and Blackledge (2018), ensures that students can follow along without getting lost, thereby maintaining engagement and participation. This scaffolding technique is beneficial in subjects requiring precise understanding, such as mathematics and science, where conceptual clarity is crucial. Moreover, code-switching also plays a vital role in validating and respecting students' linguistic and cultural backgrounds. Educators can create a sense of belonging and affirmation by incorporating students' home languages into the classroom. Palmer et. al (2018) found that students who see their languages represented in their learning environment tend to have higher self-esteem and are more motivated to participate. This inclusivity supports language development and fosters a positive emotional and psychological climate in the classroom. Carrying out a study among Portuguese-speaking university students learning English, Shafi et al. (2019) pointed out that the teacher changes his/her language to the student's native language when dealing with specific grammar points taught at that moment. The study's findings further revealed that the teacher switched codes from L2 to L1 to clarify their understanding of grammatical structure. This led the learners to reflect on the form under analysis and facilitated their understanding. Finally, Abad (2020) found that code-switching

is particularly helpful in simplifying the meaning of difficult words or abstract concepts to the level of competence and experience of the learners. The speech mode has also created a low-anxiety classroom atmosphere conducive to learning.

3.3.2. *Applying the right function of code-switching*—As stated, everything is good if done in moderation. Employing code-switching in a language class, especially if done frequently, can hamper students' language learning. As a result, another insight gathered from the interviews is the application of the right function of code-switching. It implies that code-switching should be done only when needed and should be done with a purpose or goal in mind; this is to not obstruct the goal, which is language learning. The following insight is extracted from the narratives shared by the teacher participants. Their responses in the in-depth interview have supported the above-mentioned theme. IDI 3, IDI 4, and IDI 5 have shared that applying code-switching with the proper function and purpose helps achieve goals such as fluency, effective communication, and better understanding. Coinciding with the above-mentioned point are the following studies that inferred the same insights from their respective undertaking. Creese and Blackledge (2018) opined that code-switching should be perceived as an opportunity to apply the proper function of the concept rather than the hurdles it gives. The author is trying to imply that the employment of code-switching should be done correctly and should be the focus instead of the possible negative impacts.

To further support the theme mentioned, the focus group discussion also shared their insights on the functions and setbacks presented by employing code-switching in the classroom. FGD 8, FGD 9, and FGD 10 have acknowledged code-switching's significant role in communication. Code-switching gives the students the capacity to express their thoughts freely and com-

fortably. In line with that, Enama (2018) also believed that code-switching should be applied purposively. He believes that it should be done in partnership between the languages involved. He further argued that L1 should support the target language learning in one framework, so there is no burden of employing L1 because it serves a precise function in the classroom for the students. Meanwhile, Zhu (2018) posited that the long-term alternation of language also induces errors as standard forms without realizing that they stick to the standards. Hence, the author expressed reservations about the application of code-switching as it can pose more disadvantages and may affect the way students communicate later on. However, in response to that and in connection to the application of the right function of code-switching in the class, Jacobson (1983, as cited from Nurhamidah et. al (2018) proposed criteria for code-switching instruction in the classroom. These are the following: the distribution of languages must be 50/50, the alternation must be unconscious, and the alternation must be for the sake of the learning goal. Those criteria are not an absolute prerequisite for all teachers but if it does not meet the criteria, Jacobson mentions it as unstructured code-switching.

3.3.3. A bridge from the known to the unknown—The final theme for the insights on the perception and setbacks experienced by teachers in employing code-switching in their language learning classrooms. Code-switching serves as a bridge between the known (native language) and the unknown (second language). From the interview conducted, participants have shared that code-switching has different functions, such as repetitive function and affective function. Teachers also have knowledge of the importance of effective communication.

The abovementioned participants have mentioned the importance of code-switching for students' adjustment to learning the target language. IDI 1 has stated that this sociolinguistic

phenomenon benefits the students and the teachers inside the classroom. Meanwhile, IDI 2 shared the same insight. Language learning is a difficult undertaking; hence, one should move slowly and surely to avoid problems along the way. IDI 4 also pointed out that code-switching gives the students resources that will help them in their language learning. Further supporting the theme, Shafi et al. (2019) stated that the student's attention is directed to the new knowledge by making use of code-switching and, accordingly, making use of the native language. Thus, it can be seen as a bridge from the known to the unknown. The participants shared in the focus group discussion that code-switching is significant in language learning. FGD 9 has mentioned that the positive impact of code-switching should go unnoticed. Meanwhile, FGD 6 and FGD 8 reiterated that code-switching is necessary to aid students' understanding. This is consistent with the idea of García and Kleyn (2018). They argued that when teachers switch to a student's native language to explain difficult concepts, the student grasps the new material more effectively. This approach reduces the cognitive load associated with learning in a second language by anchoring new information in the familiar framework of the student's first language, thus bridging the gap between what students already know and what they need to learn. Creese and Blackledge (2018) discuss how this scaffolding technique supports students in gradually acquiring proficiency in the second language without feeling overwhelmed. By initially presenting information in a familiar language and then reinforcing it in the target language, teachers can facilitate a smoother transition and deeper understanding of the subject matter. Similarly, from the findings of Palmer et al. (2018), the use of code-switching also validates and respects students' linguistic and cultural backgrounds, which is crucial for their confidence and motivation. Acknowledging and incorporating students' home

Fig. 5. Insights Gained from the Experiences and Coping Mechanisms Employed by Secondary English Teachers

languages in the classroom fosters a sense of belonging and boosts their confidence to engage with new content. This inclusive approach not only bridges the known to the unknown but also promotes a more positive and effective learning environment where students feel valued and understood. Gort and Pontier (2019) suggest that professional development and training are essential for teachers to master code-switching techniques. With the right skills, teachers can

use code-switching to seamlessly connect prior knowledge with new learning, thus creating a more coherent and inclusive educational experience. Figure 5 shows Insights gained from the experiences and coping mechanisms employed by secondary English and the emergence of the three themes: code-switching as an emerging language pedagogy, a bridge from known to the unknown, and applying the right function of code-switching.

4. Implications and Future Directions

This chapter presents the study summary. From the summary of the findings, I draw the implications and future directions. The purpose of my study was to discover lived experiences, coping mechanisms, and insights regarding code-switching in an ESL classroom through the teachers’ lens. In order to achieve the research objectives, I used a qualitative phenomenological method with the use of thematic analysis. In adherence to Creswell’s (2019) guidelines in open-ended questions for interviews were applied to get an authentic understanding of people’s experiences. Furthermore, through this interview approach, I encouraged my participants to fully and openly discuss their own definition or meaning of the phenomenon being explored, which were the narratives of secondary English teachers about using code-switching.

4.1. Findings—Based on the results of the thematic analysis of the responses from the participants of the study, the following find-

ings, and their corresponding themes were revealed: the lived experiences of secondary English teachers about the employment of code-

switching were repetitive function, affective function, impedes the student's learning of L2, and causes a decline in the language proficiency and confidence of students. Meanwhile, the coping mechanisms employed by secondary English teachers were effective communication, minimizing the utilization of code-switching, and encouraging the use of L2. The insights drawn from the findings of the study were: code-switching as an emerging language pedagogy, the application of the right function of code-switching in the classroom, and a bridge from the known to the unknown. In light of the secondary English teachers' lived experiences regarding code-switching, four (4) emerging themes were identified based on the participants' responses. The first one is the acknowledgment of code-switching's repetitive function. This function pertains to repeating an instruction, a word, or a phrase in English into the learners' L1. This is done in order to clarify meaning or check for comprehension. According to the participants, the repetitive function of code-switching has helped assist students' understanding as well as ensuring that the class has achieved the set goals and objectives. The second theme discussed is code-switching's affective function. In a language classroom, students may have the tendency to be conscious of utilizing the target language, which may have a ripple effect on the way they express their thoughts. However, code-switching not only helps students deliver their thoughts thoroughly, but it also helps them feel safe and at ease in slowly adapting to their second language. Moreover, the affective function also covers the creation of a cheerful learning ambiance. The third experience is that code-switching impedes students' learning of their L2. The teachers have expressed their worry about how code-switching has the potential to obstruct or delay the students' learning of English. They have also mentioned that if code-switching is employed excessively in the classroom, it may have negative effects on the students. The fourth experience is the decline in students' language proficiency and confidence. As participants stated, the frequent employment of code-switching might directly impact the students' language learning. Instead of assisting them, it can hamper their progress. Alongside that was the decline in students' confidence in using English. They were more conscious and uncomfortable if they were not used to conversing in English. On the other hand, the coping mechanisms teachers employed had three (3) themes. The first one was effective communication. As the participants mentioned, code-switching has the tendency to obstruct the students' learning of their L2. To prevent or avoid that from happening, the teachers utilize effective communication in their classroom. That way, the students can learn their L2, and the teachers can achieve their educational goals. The second theme is the teachers encouraging the use of their second language. In the narratives shared by the teachers, they express their worry regarding the students falling behind in their language learning. In order to avoid this, teachers should encourage their students to utilize L2 whenever they are participating in the class. Meanwhile, the last theme for the second research question is minimizing the application of code-switching in the classroom. According to the participants, code-switching should be applied in moderation, especially in a language-learning class. The possibility of it hindering the language learning of students in high. Hence, the teacher employs these coping mechanisms to ensure that students still learn their L2 without any obstruction. On the other hand, in terms of language learning insights, the study has unfurled three (3) recurring themes from the participants' responses. The first one is the view of code-switching as an emerging language pedagogy. Now more than ever, language learning has been highlighted as a perk because it was a key that would open doors for new learning and great opportunities. Hence,

teachers utilize various strategies and learning pedagogies to assist students in achieving the peak of language learning. One of those pedagogies in the field of language learning is code-switching. The second insight is the application of the right function of code-switching. The sociolinguistic phenomenon has received both praise and criticism from several studies done over different years and in diverse contexts. Until today, there are still debates about its impact on language learning. However, as unfurled by this undertaking, the solution is the application of the right function of code-switching. If the application is unstructured, it may have adverse effects on students. There might still be blurry lines along the edges of code-switching, but it was clear that everything was deemed fine as long as it was done in moderation. Finally, the last theme for insight is code-switching a bridge from the known to the unknown. Language learning is a daunting task. Many students are intimidated by using English. They are often limited by their linguistic abilities, which causes a decline in their confidence. However, based on the interview, teachers have expressed that code-switching assists the students' understanding and makes them more comfortable in language learning. Based on the results of the thematic analysis of the responses from the participants of the study, the following findings and their corresponding themes were revealed: the perceptions of secondary English teachers on the employment of code-switching emphasize its repetitive function, affective function, and its function to hone effective communication. The setbacks experienced by secondary English teachers were code-switching impeding the students' learning of L2, a decline in their language proficiency and confidence, and a lowered level of language proficiency. The insights drawn from the study's findings were code-switching as an emerging language pedagogy, applying the proper function of code-switching in the classroom, and a bridge from the known to the

unknown.

4.2. *Implications*—The results of my analysis revealed the following significant findings. Language learning has received growing attention throughout the years. Its advantages have been realized in the academe and almost every aspect of human endeavor. In response, language learning in schools has been strengthened, and several language pedagogies have been injected with the desire to help students achieve the educational goals they set for themselves. Code-switching has been around for a long time in language learning. Many may have employed it without knowing or unconsciously. However, this sociolinguistic phenomenon has an immense impact on students' journeys in language learning. In the Philippines, where English was labeled as the second language, the importance placed upon learning or even mastering it was excellent. As it was planted in the people's minds, being bilingual was a perk. Along with the great importance of it comes the great desire to learn it as early as possible. Hence, English was a subject from elementary to high school and is deemed one of the mediums for instruction. Nevertheless, no journey was easy, especially if it was a journey towards learning. It was a painful yet fulfilling process that does not exempt language learning. Therefore, teachers often find themselves employing code-switching for a variety of reasons. One of these was its function of clarifying meaning through repetition; another was its function in the affective aspect and in building a cheerful learning ambiance. However, with praise comes criticism. Despite having a list of the advantages it may bring to a language learning class, code-switching also poses possible setbacks. These setbacks include impeding the students' learning of L2 and causing a decline in students' language proficiency and confidence. The converging viewpoints on code-switching are both beneficial in terms of improving language learning and learning how to prevent the adverse

effects from happening. Despite all that, code-switching has been viewed as a converging language pedagogy and is deemed beneficial when coupled with applying its proper function. Only then can an ideal learning atmosphere where language learning can grow and prosper be made. Meanwhile, Hoffman's (1991) theory of code-switching encapsulates the functions of code-switching presented by the participants through in-depth interviews and focus group discussions. The theory postulated seven reasons why we code-switch. The first theme under the first research question, which focuses on the repetitive function of code-switching, was included in the reasons presented by the theory. The second theme under the first research question was the affective function of code-switching. This was also included in the reasons under Hoffman's theory. It also coincides with the Speech Accommodation Theory by Giles and Powesland (1975, as cited from Boztec, 2003). Meanwhile, the third theme under the first research question can also be found in the Theory of Code-Switching. The theory of code-switching has given us reasons for and purposes for code-switching in the classroom. It could be used in various ways as long as it is coupled with awareness of the context and responsibility so that adverse effects can be avoided. Meanwhile, the Speech Accommodation Theory explains the interplay between the teacher and students or the speaker and the interlocutors. For effective communication, both parties' attitudes and interests should be apparent. These theories have helped the researcher further understand the sociolinguistic phenomenon.

4.3. Future Directions—Based on the study's findings, the findings needed to be adequately relayed and used by the significant people for whom this research was intended. The educational leaders. The findings of the undertaking would raise awareness among educational leaders on the status of language learning in ESL classrooms. This includes the ex-

periences and coping mechanisms the teachers have gone through. Once they can recognize and reflect on this existing scenario, they can provide teachers with ample support and assistance to improve the delivery of instruction. Furthermore, the fundamental move educational leaders can provide is to generate strategies for teachers to apply in their EFL classrooms. Another is by providing materials, especially reading materials like books written in English, to aid the students' language learning. The school principals or heads can be informed about their respective schools' current language learning situation and check on the students' progress. The school heads may support the teachers by providing more language learning resources to offer students a variety of learning experiences to deepen and widen their interest in learning a different language. They can also hold meetings to encourage the teachers to be more open about their thoughts and emotions so that the school can provide guidance and support. Teachers. Language teachers may find a good rapport on the findings of the study by leaning on the perceptions and the setbacks experienced by teachers. The findings would also enable them to know the proper function of code-switching and how to properly apply it in class without compromising the students' learning of their L2. Learners. The study's findings would benefit the learners, for they would realize the positive and negative effects of code-switching. They may also discover how code-switching may support or hinder their language learning. Most importantly, the findings would raise awareness among the learners about how code-switching should be utilized to assist them in their language learning journey. Internal and external stakeholders. They may provide support to enhance the teaching-learning experience in teaching and achieving fluency and proficiency in language learning. They may provide opportunities for students to learn and grow outside the academe, such as immersion, where they can

use what they have learned in the real world. The stakeholders may be the source of other ways and means to solve some of the challenges teachers face. Future researchers may conduct the study but take the students' perspective to compare whether the teachers and students share the same view on the application of code-switching. Uncovering the students' perspective on this matter was vital, for their learning was deemed more important; thus, gathering their thoughts would substantially contribute to the body of knowledge in this field.

5. References

- Abad, L. (2019). Code-switching: An alternative resource in teaching science and math [Retrieved from <https://ejournals.ph/article.php?id=3486>].
- Agna, A., Molina, C., Pontillas, M., & Ignacio, J. (2022). Exploring codeswitching occurrences in an online english language learning in a state college, philippines. *Journal of Education, Management and Development Studies*. <https://doi.org/10.1093/fampra/13.6.522>
- Aljoundi, E. (2013). The strengths and weaknesses of code-switching and bilingualism in the language classroom. <https://doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.1.5051.1762>
- Baker, C. (1995). *A parents' and teachers' guide to bilingualism*. Multilingual Matters publishers. <https://benthamopen.com/contents/pdf/TOALJ/TOALJ-3-10.pdf>
- Becker, C. (1992). *Living and relating: An introduction to phenomenology*. Sage. <https://doi.org/https://dx.doi.org/10.24093/awej/vol7no2.32>
- Bergsleithne, J. (2012). Grammar and interaction in the efl classroom: A sociocultural study [Retrieved from <https://search.trdizin.gov.tr/yayin/detay/318002/code-switching-in-tertiary-level-efl-classrooms-perceptions-of-teachers>].
- Borlongan, A. M. (2012). Reflecting on the use of code-switching in philippine education today. *TESOL Journal*, 7, 78–80.
- Boztepe, E. (2003). Issues in code-switching: Competing models and theories [Retrieved from <https://academiccommons.columbia.edu/doi/10.7916/D8M04H7G/download>].
- Cipriani, F. (2011). Oral participation strategies in the foreign language classroom: An ethnographic account [Retrieved from <https://www.researchgate.net/profile/Hoang-Yen-Phuong/>]
- Cook, V. J. (2012). Multicompetence [In C. Chapelle (Ed.), *The encyclopedia of applied linguistics*. Retrieved from https://www.researchgate.net/publication/259424073_own-language_use_in
- Blackledge, A. (2018). *The routledge handbook of language and identity*. Routledge <https://doi.org/10.1080/13632043.2018.1315696>
- Creswell, J. (2012). *Educational research: Planning, conducting, and evaluating quantitative and qualitative research*. Pearson.
- De Castro, N. P. G., Parajito, G. P., Realco, J. M. B., & Dacara, J. R. C. (2021). The effects of code-switching to the communicative competence of 21st century learners: A case study. *Universitas*, 9(1), 1–1.
- Denzin, N. K., & Lincoln, Y. S. (2000). Introduction: The discipline and practice of qualitative research. In N. K. Denzin & Y. S. Lincoln (Eds.), *Handbook of qualitative research* (2nd, pp. 1–28). Sage.
- Department of Health. (2020). Guidelines on the risk-based public health standards for covid-19 [<https://doh.gov.ph/sites/default/files/health-update/a02020-0015.pdf>].
- Duff, P. A. (2018). Case study research in applied linguistics [Retrieved from <https://www.reseat/pu>

- Dykhanova, A. (2015). *Functions of code-switching and attitudes toward them: A case study* [Master's thesis]. Eastern Mediterranean University (EMU)-Doğu Akdeniz Üniversitesi (DAÜ).
- Ellis, R. (2015). *Understanding second language acquisition 2nd edition: Oxford applied linguistics*. Oxford University Press.
- Enama, P. R. B. (2016). The impact of english-only and bilingual approaches to efl instruction on low-achieving bilinguals in cameroon: An empirical study. *Journal of Language Teaching and Research*. <https://doi.org/10.17507/jltr.0701.03>
- Fareed, M., Humayun, S., & Akhtar, H. (2016). English language teachers' code-switching in class: Esl learners' perceptions. *Journal of Education & Social Sciences*.
- García, O., & Wei, L. (2018). *Translanguaging: Language, bilingualism and education*. <https://doi.org/10.5565/rev/jtl3.764>
- Gkonou, C., Dewaele, J.-M., & King, J. (2020). *The emotional rollercoaster of language teaching*. Multilingual Matters. https://www.researchgate.net/publication/341567382_Introduction_to_the_Emotional_Rollercoaster_of_Language_Teaching
- Gort, M., & Pontier, R. (2019). Coordinated translanguaging pedagogy as distributed cognition: A case study of two dual language bilingual education preschool co-teachers' languaging practices during shared book readings. *DOI: 10.1080/19313152.2016.1150732*.
- Grant, L. E., & Nguyen, T. H. (2017). Code-switching in vietnamese university efl teachers' classroom instruction: A pedagogical focus. *Language Awareness*. <https://doi.org/10.1080/09658416.2017.1402915>
- Hoffman, C. (1991). *An introduction to bilingualism* [Retrieved from <https://media.neliti.com/media/EN-code-switching-in-social-media-twitter.pdf>]. Longman.
- Iyitoglu, O. (2016). Code-switching from l2 to l1 in efl classrooms [Retrieved from <https://files.eric>].
- Leoanak, S. P. P., & Amalo, B. K. (2018). Teachers' beliefs and perceptions of code switching in english as foreign language classroom. *SHS Web of Conferences*, 42, 00034.
- Lin, A. (2013). Classroom code-switching: Three decades of research [Retrieved from <https://www.researchgate.net/publication/25736288449>]. *Applied Linguistics Review*.
- Lincoln, Y. S., & Guba, E. G. (1985). *Naturalistic inquiry* [Retrieved from <https://ethnographyworkshop.files.wordpress.com/2014/11/lincoln-guba-1985-establishing-trustworthiness-naturalistic-inquiry.pdf>]. Sage Publications.
- Loewen, S., Isbell, D. R., & Spino, L. A. (2019). The effectiveness of second language interaction for language learning. *Language-Learning*. https://www.researchgate.net/publication/311571290_Review_of_Language_Learning_with_Digital_Video
- Macaro, E. (2019). *The psychology of the language learner: Individual differences in second language acquisition*. Oxford University Press. <https://doi.org/10.1017/S0261444821000483>
- Marshall, M. N. (1996). Sampling for qualitative research <http://dx.doi.org/10.1093/fampra/13.6.522>]. *Family Practice*, 13(6), 522–525.
- McKay, S. L., & Wong, S.-L. C. (2019). *The bilingual edge: Why, when, and how to teach your child a second language*. HarperCollins. <https://doi.org/10.2478/sm-2021-0011>
- McNamara, C. (1999). Basics of conducting focus groups [Available from <http://www.mapnp.org>].
- Mercer, S., & Dornyei, Z. (2020). *Engaging language learners in contemporary classrooms*. <https://doi.org/10.1017/9781009024563>
- Metila, A. (2019). Functions of code-switching in a language classroom [Retrieved from <https://jour>

- Naeem, S. (2019). Internal validity in research. helping research writing for student and professional researchers [Retrieved from <http://researcharticles.com/index.php/internal-validity-research/>].
- Nordquist, R. (2019). Learn the function of code-switching as a linguistic code [Retrieved from <https://www.thoughtco.com/code-switching-language-1689858>].
- Nurhamidah, Fauziati, E., & Supriyadi, S. (2018). Code-switching in efl classroom: Is it good or bad? *Journal of English Education*. <https://doi.org/10.31327/jee.v3i2.861>
- Ogechi, N. O. (2019). Ethnicity, language, and identity in kenya. *Modern Africa: Politics, History and Society*. <https://doi.org/10.26806/modafr.v7i.265>
- Palmer, D., Martinez, R., Mateus, S., & Henderson, K. (2018). Reframing the debate on language separation: Toward a vision for translanguaging pedagogies in the dual language classroom. *Journal of Language, Identity & Education*. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1540-4781.2014.12121.x>
- Peregoy, S. F., & Boyle, O. F. (2013). *Reading, writing and learning in esl: A resource book for teaching k-12 english learners* [Retrieved from <https://commons.mtholyoke.edu/wp-content/uploads/sites/227/2016/06/First-and-second-language-acquisition-Peregoy-Boyle-2013-p.->].
- Polio, C. G., & Duff, P. A. (1994). Teachers' language use in university foreign language classrooms: A qualitative analysis of english and target language alternation. *The Modern Language Journal*, 78(3), 313–326.
- Rankin, A. (2023). What is a foreign language? [Retrieved from <https://www.languagehumanities.org/what-is-a-foreign-language.htm>].
- Razak, S. A., & Shah, P. M. (2020). The students' beliefs on using code-switching in the esl classrooms. *International Journal of Academic Research in Business and Social Sciences*, 10(2). <https://doi.org/10.6007/ijarbss/v10-i2/6918>
- Republic Act 10173 – Data Privacy Act of 2012. National Privacy Commission. (2021, November). Republic act 10173 – data privacy act of 2012 [Retrieved from <https://www.privacy.gov.ph/data-privacy-act/>].
- Ritchie, J., & Spencer, L. (1994). Qualitative data analysis for applied policy research. In A. Bryman & R. Burgess (Eds.), *Anal. qual. data* (pp. 173–194). Routledge. https://doi.org/10.4324/9780203413081_chapter_9
- Sayer, P., & Ban, R. (2020). Translanguaging in the secondary classroom: Using multiple languages to meet students' diverse needs. *Journal of Language, Identity & Education*. <https://doi.org/10.1080/19313152.2016.1150732>
- Shafi, S., Kazmi, S., & Asif, R. (2019). Benefits of code-switching in language learning classroom at university of education lahore. <https://doi.org/10.21744/irjmis.v7n1.842>
- Sondang, L., & Bonik, A. (2017). Teachers' beliefs and perceptions of code switching in english as foreign language classroom. In *Shs web of conferences* (p. 00034, Vol. 42). <https://doi.org/10.1051/shsconf/20184200034>
- Stanage, S. M. (1987). *Adult education and phenomenological research: New directions for theory, practice, and research*. <https://doi.org/10.1080/09500782.2011.573076>
- Torres, R. L. (2023). Code-switching in the efl classroom: Yeah or nay? *International Multidisciplinary Research Journal*. <https://doi.org/10.54476/ioer-imrj/142140>

- Turnbull, M., & Dailey-O’Cain, J. (2020). *First language use in second and foreign language learning*. Multilingual Matters. https://www.researchgate.net/publication/324594510_First_Language_Use_in_Second_and_Foreign_Language_Learning
- Üstunel, E. (2016). Efl classroom code-switching [Retrieved from https://www.researchgate.net/publication/329492888_SWITCHING_IN_EFL_CLASSROOM_SETTING].
- Uys, D., & Van Dulm, O. (2011). The function of classroom code-switching in the siyanda district of the northern cape. *Southern African Linguistics and Applied Language Studies*. <https://doi.org/10.2989/16073614.2011.583159>
- Xu, Q. (2010). To switch or not to switch: Examine the code-switching practices of teachers of non-english majors/changer ou ne pas changer: Examiner les pratique de l’alternance de code de l’enseignement de l’anglais pour les étudiants non-anglophones. *Canadian Social Science*, 6(4), 109–.
- Yaakub, H. Z. H., Ghani, D. L. P. P. A., Sulaiman, H. S. H., Hitam, S. H., & Heng, C. S. (2013). Codeswitching in universities in brunei darussalam and malaysia. *Codeswitching in University English-Medium Classes: Asian Perspectives*, 36, 144.
- Younas, M., Arshad, S., Akram, K., Faisal, M., Akhtar, M., & Sarfraz, K. (2014). Code-switching and code-mixing a case of efl teachers affecting l2 learners’ learners’ learning. *Language in India*.
- Zabrodskaia, A. (2017). Russian-estonian code switching in the university [Retrieved from <https://files.eric.ed.gov/fulltext/EJ1241966.pdf>].
- Zhu, H. (2018). Dueling language, dueling values: Code switching in bilingual intergenerational conflict talk in diasporic families. *Journal of Pragmatics*. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j>.